

Determinants of Patients' Satisfaction at the General Out-Patient Clinic of the Federal Medical Centre Makurdi, Benue State

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ABSTRACT

Patients' satisfaction is an important indicator of quality health care services in a facility. The emerging global trend in patient-centered care has made patient satisfaction stand out as an imperative tool in accessing the quality of health care globally. The study aimed at accessing the level of patient satisfaction and its determinants among patient attending the General Outpatient Clinic (GOPC) of Federal Medical Center (FMC) Makurdi. This was a cross-sectional study of 178 participants who attended the GOPC. Informed consent was obtained and data was collected by an interviewer-administered questionnaire. The Data was analyzed with the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 17.0. The general satisfaction at the GOPC was significantly associated with registration process, care and concern shown by the nurses, registration time, consultation time, condition of the consulting room, waiting time in the waiting room and doctor-patient interaction. The determinants of patients' satisfaction in this study were the following: satisfaction with registration time, satisfaction with waiting in the waiting room and satisfaction with the condition of the consulting room.

Keywords: Patients satisfaction, General Outpatient Clinic, FMC Makurdi

INTRODUCTION

Patient satisfaction is defined as the extent to which patients feel that their needs and expectations are being met by a service provider.¹ The level of satisfaction with the process and products of care coupled with the judgment of the quality and outcome of care has become an integral part of the current health care delivery.^{1,2} Most

health care facilities in developing countries have neglected patient satisfaction as a vital component of quality health care service.¹ At present, emphasis is more on the operative and technological component of health care delivery which aims at satisfying the criteria stipulated by the World Health Organization.³ To a large extent, the

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psychosocial aspect of patient satisfaction which is vital in patient centered care had been neglected. The emerging global trend in patient-centered care has made patient satisfaction stand out as an imperative tool in assessing the quality of care in the health industry.⁴ Patients satisfaction affects the profitability of the health industry and has been employed in various organizations to evaluate service quality.^{2,4} A facility that offers high-quality health care services often produces a high degree of patient satisfaction.^{1,4} Satisfied patients are more likely to be adherent to follow-up, and utilize the services in the facility again.⁴ They take up less time in the consultation room and are more adherent to medication.⁵ Patients satisfaction at the GOPC could be affected by different categories of waiting time. Other factors affecting patient satisfaction are the attitudes of the health care workers at the registration point, concern shown by nurses to the patient, the condition of the consultation room and doctor-patient interaction in the consultation room.

Anecdotally, there is a rising burden of patients' dissatisfaction with the consultation processes in many health institutions. These complaints range from the physical discomfort of patients, long waiting time, staff attitude, respect for patients' preference and occasional denial of services. This trend needs to be addressed being that the GOPC is a gate into the health care system and also an indicator to the quality of health care services being delivered in the facility. The dissatisfaction of patients at the GOPC is of grave concern to the Primary Care Physician who is the custodian of Patient-Centered Care Model that emphasizes patient satisfaction.

Patient dissatisfaction with healthcare providers could be attributed to the knowledge gap about patient needs in the primary, secondary and tertiary healthcare facilities.^{3,4} This knowledge gap has resulted in poor health-seeking behaviour and non-adherence to the treatment regimen. This study can deliver some of the information needed to fill this gap.

The study aims to access the level of patient satisfaction and its determinants among patients attending the General Outpatient Clinic (GOPC) of Federal Medical

Centre Makurdi. This would broaden the physician's insight on the inimitable viewpoint of health care consumers with consideration of their rights, privileges, and opportunities. This study will also draw the physicians' attention to work with the principle of the patient-centered clinical methods (PCCM) with its immense benefits.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was a cross-sectional study involving 178 patients aged 18 years and above attending the General Out-Patient Clinic (GOPC) of Federal Medical Center Makurdi in Benue State in Nigeria. The patients were selected by systematic sampling method. This method involves choosing a random starting point and a sample interval with which a sample group is selected from the targeted population. The selection technique was employed in this study for over three months (February 2021 to April 2021). Those included in the study were both old and new patients attending the GOPC. The patients that were critically ill and require immediate attention or admission were excluded.

The Federal Medical Centre Makurdi is a four hundred bedded tertiary health institution and comprises four satellite centres; the Mission ward, Psychiatric and Dental complex, ART (antiretroviral therapy) Specialist Clinic and the permanent site at Apir. The General Out-patient Clinic (GOPC) of the hospital is the first point of care for most patients seeking medical care at the facility. The GOPC and other specialist clinics run at the Permanent site, Apir. The patients obtain their GOPC cards at the records unit and proceed to the nursing station where vital signs are taken. Their names are entered into a register before they are attended to by a doctor. The clinic has eight consulting rooms operated by eight doctors whose work schedule includes consultation, admission, and referral to specialist clinics like the cardiovascular clinic. The GOPC attends to all patients without any bias for disease type, gender or age on an out-patient basis excluding those who need emergency health care services. The average monthly GOPC attendance was 2076 during the period of this study.

The questionnaire was interviewer-administered and pretested at the specialist clinic. The research assistants were resident doctors in Family Medicine. They were trained on the objectives of the study and how to administer the questionnaire. The first part of the questionnaire (section A) obtained information on the socio-demographic characteristics; the second part (Section B) obtained information on the category of waiting time and the overall patient satisfaction with clinical services. The third part (Section C) measured the level of satisfaction after the doctor-patient interaction in the consulting room.

Definition of Terms: Registration time (RT): considered as the length of time from when a patient arrives at the clinic, until when he/she received a clinic card. Clinic wait time (CWT) (time spent in the waiting area): considered as the length of time from when the patient receives a clinic card, until when he/she enters the consultation room. Consultation time (CT): considered as the length of time from when the patient enters the consultation room, until when he/she comes out of the consultation room. Total clinic waiting time (TCWT): considered as the length of time from when the patient arrives at the clinic until when he/she comes out of the consultation room.

The data obtained was analyzed using SPSS version 17.0. The categorical variables were summarized by frequency distribution and cross-tabulation. The dependent variable was the overall patient satisfaction at the GOPC of Federal Medical Centre Makurdi. The independent variables include the socio-demographic characteristics, the categories of waiting time and patients' satisfaction with clinical services. Chi-square was used to test associations between categorical variables. Multivariate logistic regression analysis was performed to identify independent variables predicting overall general patient satisfaction at the GOPC. The level of statistical significance was set at 5% ($p < 0.05$).

RESULTS

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (N=178)

Socio-demographic Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Age (years)		
≤ 20	13	7.3
21-40	83	46.6
41-60	60	33.7
≥61	22	12.7
Gender		
Male	83	46.6
Female	95	53.4
Marital status		
Currently married	63	35.4
Currently not married*	115	64.5
Ethnic group		
Tiv	136	76.4
Idoma	16	9
Igede	5	2.8
Others	21	11.8
Religion		
Christian	170	95.5
Moslem	7	3.9
Traditional	1	0.6
Level of education		
Informal	23	12.9
Primary	29	16.3
Secondary	62	34.8
Tertiary	64	36.0
Place of residence		
Urban	120	67.4
Rural	58	32.6
Occupation		
Student	28	15.7
Farming	55	30.9
Business	55	30.9
Civil servant	28	15.7
**Others	12	6.7

*Currently not married: Divorced, widow and widowers, singles

**Other: Artisan, retirees, applicants,

Table 1 shows participants' socio-demographic characteristics. Out of the 178 participants recruited for the study, most of the participants 83(46.6%) were in the age group (21-40) years. A higher proportion of the participants 95(53.4%) were females while 83(46.6%) were males. More than two-thirds of the participants 115(64.5) were not currently married while 63(35.4%) of the participants were married. Most of the participants 136(76.4%) were of Tiv ethnicity and an overwhelming majority 170(95.5%) were Christians. A higher proportion of the participants 64(36.6%) had tertiary education while only 23(12.9%) of the participants had informal education. Most of the participants 120(67.4%) reside in the urban area and almost 110(61.8%) of the participants' occupation were farming and business.

Table 2: Categories of timing at the GOPC of Federal Medical Centre Makurdi

	Registration time (Minutes)	Clinic waiting time (Minutes)	Consultation tim (Minutes)	Total clinic waiting time (Minutes)
Mean	15	109	11	134
Mode	12	102	10	104
Minimum	1	9	2	23
Maximum	61	240	47	304

Table 2 showed that the mean registration time was 15 minutes. The mean clinic waiting time was 109 minutes. The average consultation time was 11 minutes. The shortest time spent in the consultation room was 2 minutes and the longest duration of time spent with the doctor was 47 minutes. The average total waiting time was 134 minutes

Table 3: Participants' responses on satisfaction with clinic services at the GOPC

SN	Variables	Satisfied n(%)	Not satisfied n(%)
1	Are you satisfied with the reception you had on arrival at the clinic?	161(90.4)	17(9.6)
2	Are you satisfied with the registration process?	157(88.2)	21(11.8)
3	Are you satisfied with the care and concern shown by the nurses?	166(93.3)	12(6.7)
4	Are you satisfied with the registration time?	173(97.2)	5(2.8)
5	Are you satisfied with the consultation time?	173(97.2)	5(2.8)
6	Are you satisfied with the condition of the consulting room?	156(87.6)	22(12.4)
7	Are you satisfied with the waiting time in the waiting area?	161(90.4)	17(9.6)
8	Are you satisfied with patient /doctor interaction?	172(96.6)	6(3.4)
9	Are you generally satisfied with the overall services at the GOPC?	162(91)	16(9)

Table 3 shows the participants responses to clinical services. A high proportion of the participants 162(91%) were satisfied with the overall services at the GOPC of FMC Makurdi.

Table 4: Association between socio-demographic variables and the overall satisfaction with services at the GOPC

	General satisfaction of overall services at the GOPC		χ^2	df	p-value
	Satisfied (n%)	Not satisfied(n%)			
Age group			2.17	3	0.54
≤ 20	2(15.4)	11(84.6)			
21-40	9(10.8)	74(89.2)			
41-60	3(5.0)	57(75.0)			
≥61	2(9.1)	20(90.9)			
Gender			8.5	1	0.04
Male	70(84.2)	13(15.7)			
Female	92(96.8)	3(3.2)			
Marital status			1.6	1	0.20
Currently married	107(93)	8(7)			
Currently not married	55(87.3)	8(12.7)			
Ethnic group			2.7	3	0.50
Tiv	122(89.7)	14(10.3)			
Idoma	16(100)	0(0)			
Igede	5(100)	0(0)			
Others	19(90.5)	2(9.5)			
Religion			0.83	2	0.67
Christianity	154(90.6)	16(9.4)			
Moslem	7(100)	0(0)			
Traditional	1(100)	0(0)			
Level of education			3.3	3	0.35
Informal	22(95)	1(4.3)			
Primary	27(93.1)	2(6.9)			
Secondary	58(85.9)	4(6.5)			
Tertiary	55(85.9)	9(14.1)			
Occupation			2.3	4	0.67
Student	24(85.7)	4(14.3)			
Farming	51(92.7)	4(7.3)			
Business	51(92.7)	4(7.3)			
Civil servant	26(92.9)	2(7.1)			
Other Vocation	10(83.3)	2(16.7)			
Place of residence			0.014	1	0.905
Rural	53(91.4)	5(8.6)			
Urban	109(90.8)	11(9.2)			

Table 4 shows the association between the socio-demographic characteristic and overall satisfaction with services at the GOPC. A higher proportion of the female participants 92(96.8%) were satisfied with the overall services at the GOPC compare to their male counterpart. The relationship between the female gender and overall satisfaction at the GOPC was statistically significant ($\chi^2=8.5$, $df=1$, $p=0.04$)

Table 5: Association between other variables and overall satisfaction with the services at the GOPC

	General satisfaction of overall services at the GOPC		χ^2	df	p-value
	Satisfied (n%)	Not satisfied (n%)			
Satisfaction with the reception on arrival at the clinic			33	1	0.000
Satisfied	153(95)	8(5)			
Not satisfied	9(52.9)	8(47.1)			
Satisfaction with registration process			24.7	1	0.000
Satisfied	149(94.9)	8(5.1)			
Not satisfied	13(61.9)	8(38.1)			
Satisfaction with care and concern shown by nurses			38.3	1	0.000
Satisfied	157(94.6)	9(5.4)			
Not satisfied	5(41.7)	7(58.3)			
Satisfied with registration time			81	1	0.000
Satisfied	156(97.5)	4(2.5)			
Not satisfied	6(33.5)	12(66.7)			
Satisfied with consultation time			31.7	1	0.000
Satisfied	161(93.1)	12(6.9)			
Not satisfied	1(20)	4(80)			
Satisfied with the condition of the consulting room			63.7	1	0.000
Satisfied	152(97.4)	4(2.6)			
Not satisfied	10(45.5)	12(54.5)			
Satisfied with waiting time in the waiting area			71.3	1	0.000
Satisfied	156(96.9)	5(3.1)			
Not satisfied	6(35.3)	11(64.7)			
Satisfied with patient/doctors interaction			63.7	1	0.000
Satisfied	159(97.4)	4(2.6)			
Not satisfied	2(33.3)	4(66.7)			

Table 5 shows the association between satisfaction with clinical services and the overall satisfaction with the GOPC services.

The overall satisfaction with services at the GOPC was significantly associated with all clinical services which include reception on arrival at the clinic, registration process, care and concern shown by the nurses, registration time, consultation time, condition of the consulting room, waiting time in the waiting area and doctors/patient interaction all with $p=0.000$

Table 6: Logistic regression model of independent variables predicting overall general satisfaction at the GOPC

Variables	B	p-	aOR	95% Confidential interval	
				Lower	Upper
Satisfaction with registration process	-958	0.217	0.141	0.06	3.150
Satisfaction with the reception on arrival at the clinic	0.989	0.487	2.689	0.166	43.673
Satisfaction with nursing care and concern	2.036	0.087	7.663	0.747	78.643
Satisfaction with registration time	3.228	0.010	25.225	3.485	182.567
Satisfaction with consultation time	1.564	0.705	4.777	0.001	15483.941
Satisfaction with waiting to see a doctor in the waiting area	3.029	0.003	20.684	2.732	156.605
Satisfaction with doctor's consulting room	3.348	0.045	28.448	1.082	747.690

Note: Omnibus test of model coefficient: $\chi^2 = 64.08$, $df=9$, $p < 0.000$; Hosmer-Lemeshow test: $\chi^2 = 10.12$, $df=5$, $p = 0.072$

Table 6 shows the logistic regression model of the independent variables predicting overall general satisfaction at the GOPC. The independent variables eligible to be entered into the logistic regression model were satisfaction with the reception on arrival at the clinic, satisfaction with the registration process, satisfaction with care and concern shown by nurses, satisfaction with registration time, satisfaction with consultation time, satisfaction with the condition of the consulting room, satisfaction with waiting time in the waiting area and satisfaction with patient-doctors interaction.

DISCUSSION

The study aimed at knowing the level of patients' satisfaction and its determinants among participants attending the Federal Medical Centre, Makurdi. Most of the participants, 46.6% were within the age range (21-40), this age group is the most productive and active in seeking satisfactory health care services in the population.¹ The age range in this study agreed with that of Daramola in Abuja, North-central Nigeria and Enabulele in Edo state, Nigeria where the majority of the participants were also within the reproductive age group.^{1,6} The level of the overall general satisfaction at the GOPC in this study was 91%. The high proportion of satisfaction in this study is similar to the findings in Abuja, Lagos and Nnewi which were 94.8%, 94% and 84% respectively.⁸⁻¹⁰ Similarly, higher proportion have been reported in Canada, the Balkan countries and Bangladesh.¹¹⁻¹³ Contrary to the high rate of satisfaction, some studies have reported a lower proportion of satisfaction. The study by Babalola and colleagues in Ondo Nigeria reported a satisfaction rate of 62.2% while Khan and colleague reported a satisfactory rate of 41% in Pakistan.^{14,15} The higher proportion of satisfaction in this study could be attributed to the efficiency of record staffs and nurses giving prompt attention to patients at the various service points.

There was a statistically significant association between

overall general satisfaction at the GOPC and the following variables: satisfaction with the reception on arrival at the clinic, satisfaction with the registration process, satisfaction with care and concern shown by the nurses, satisfaction with the registration time, satisfaction with consultation time and satisfaction with the condition of the consulting room ($p=0.000$). The findings agree with the study by Udonwa and Ogbonna in Calabar and Adamu and Oche in Sokoto state of Nigeria.^{2,16} The study by Muktar *et al* in Lahore, Pakistan also highlighted these factors as significant in patients satisfaction at the outpatient clinic.¹⁷ The determinants of patients' satisfaction in this study were satisfaction with registration time, satisfaction with waiting in the waiting area and satisfaction with doctor's consulting room. This study revealed that participants who were satisfied with registration time were about 25 times more likely to be satisfied with the general GOPC services. The average registration time in this study was 15 minutes. Longer registration time had been recorded in the studies in Sokoto, Lagos and Owerri in Nigeria.^{2,9,18} The shorter registration time could have explained the reason for the high level of satisfaction noted in this study.

The study also revealed that participants who were satisfied with the waiting in the waiting area were 20 times more likely to be satisfied with the general services at the GOPC. The average waiting time in the waiting area was 109 minutes in this study. Studies in Edo and Abuja recorded longer waiting time with a high level of dissatisfaction.^{1,6} According to the Institute of Medicine (IOM), at least 90% of the patients should be seen within 30 minutes of their scheduled appointment time.⁶ Studies in Abuja and the Balkan countries have also reported shorter waiting time in the waiting area as a determinant of patients satisfaction.^{1,12} The longer waiting time in this study could be attributed to the increased patient load witnessed in GOPC of most public hospitals in Nigeria coupled with insufficient manpower.

This study also revealed that patients who were satisfied with doctors consulting room were 28 times more likely to be satisfied with the overall general service at the GOPC. A similar observation has been made in the study in Sokoto

and Enugu state of Nigeria.^{2,7} A study in Uganda also asserted that one of the determinants of patients' satisfaction was a conducive consulting room that ensures privacy and confidentiality of the patient.¹⁹ Patient satisfaction remains a nagging issue that needs attention in the health care delivery system. The findings in this study has thrown light at some of the areas that need improvement and the areas that need sustenance of what has been achieved.

CONCLUSION

The overall level of patients' satisfaction at GOPC was good and the determinants were: registration time, waiting time and condition of the consulting rooms

Recommendations

There should be training of record staffs with emphasis on how to receive patients and attend to them in a timely manner when they come to the record unit of the GOPC. The reception area should be conducive for patients when waiting for the doctor's consultation. There should be an advocacy for more record staff and doctors. These would reduce both the registration time and the waiting time in the reception area. The consulting rooms should be comfortable and patient's privacy should be maintained during consultation.

Limitations

The study was a cross-sectional study that looks at both the exposure and outcome simultaneously hence it may be difficult to establish causality.

This interviewed administered questionnaire relied on the honesty of respondents being interviewed. Dishonest responses will not give the correct outcome expected of the study.

The study was conducted in only one facility hence, generalizing the findings to other health care facilities in other areas may be difficult.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors had declared that no conflicting interest exists

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